

Cambodiparmarion (Gastropoda, Stylommatophora, Ariophantidae, Ostracolethinae) – a new record for the fauna of Vietnam with a description of a new species

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Abstract: A new species for science, *Cambodiparmarion bekchievi* Dedov & Vu, sp. nov., is described from South Vietnam. This is the second species in this genus, and the first one described from Vietnam. We reported the genus *Cambodiparmarion* Kuznetsov & Kuzminykh, 1999 and *C. doroshenkoi* Kuznetsov & Kuzminykh, 1999 for the first time of Vietnam. An additional finding potentially belonging to the genus is discussed.

Keywords: distribution, protected area, tropical semi-slugs, taxonomy, U Minh Ha National Park

Introduction

Cambodiparmarion was considered a monotypic genus until the present study (Schileyko 2003). The nominate species *C. doroshenkoi* has been described from a tropical forest in Kompong Som District, Kampot Province, Cambodia (Kuznetsov & Kuzminykh, 1999). The most important characters of the genus are: very thin ovate, ear-shaped, and amber coloured shell. Upper spire calcareous over periphery, basal part membranaceous. Reproductive system with rather large spermatheca with long stalk and long penis flagellum consisting of two parts: narrow proximal part and long distal part, containing axial thread and enlarged with numerous transversal folds (Kuznetsov & Kuzminykh, 1999; Schileyko, 2003). According to Kuznetsov & Kuzminykh, (1999), the species “is common in wet tropical areas near shores, where it lives on low plants during the wet season”. During the dry season, alive specimens could be found under thick layer of fallen leaves.

In this study we report the first record of *C. doroshenkoi* for Vietnam, Kien Giang Province. The second species of the genus *Cambodiparmarion* – *C. bekchievi* Dedov & Vu, sp. nov. is described from U Minh Ha National Park, Ca Mau Province, Southern Vietnam. The third juvenile specimens found in Cù Chi Tunnels Historical Park, district of Ho Chi Minh City, potentially belonging to the genus, is discussed.

Materials and methods

In the course of a survey on the invertebrate fauna of South Vietnam, several semi-slugs with a similar habitus were collected from: A) U Minh Ha National Park, Ca Mau Province; B) Mo So Cave, Kien Giang Province; C) Cù Chi Tunnels Historical Park, Ho Chi Minh City District (Fig.1). All specimens were hand collected. After photographical documentation in situ, they were processed following Nitz et al. (2009). They were relaxed in a jar with water and some drops

of the surfactant SUPRALAN-UF until fully stretched and dead. The dead semi-slug was cleaned of mucus in a sieve under cold running water. For preservation, 96% ethanol was injected with a syringe into the body cavity through the terminal tip of the sole. The specimen was then placed in ethanol (96%) and left for some hours. It was stored in 70% ethanol. The reproductive system and the shell of the semi-slug were examined under a stereomicroscope Zeiss Discovery V12 and photographed with digital camera Jenoptik Gryphax. All measurements are in millimetres and have been taken from the preserved specimen. The general methods of dissecting followed Wiktor (2000).

Used abbreviation: IBER-BAS – Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences.

Results

Order Stylommatophora A. Schmidt, 1855
Superfamily Helicarionoidea Bourguignat, 1877
Family Ariophantinae Godwin-Austen, 1883
Subfamily Ostracolethinae Simroth, 1901
Genus *Cambodiparmarion* Kuznetsov & Kuzminykh, 1999
Type species: *Cambodiparmarion doroshenkoi* Kuznetsov & Kuzminykh, 1999

Cambodiparmarion bekchievi Dedov & Vu, **sp. nov.**

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Differential diagnosis

Cambodiparmarion bekchievi Dedov & Vu, sp. nov. differs from *C. doroshenkoi* by its dark greyish-blackish colour, including the pustules and the keel of the same colour. The shell is greenish-yellowish (amber in *C. doroshenkoi*). Anatomically the new species differs by its the axial thread (AXT) of which is almost twice as long as in *C. doroshenkoi* and by its short, bulbiform distal part of the flagellum with less prominent and few in number (about 5) folds. Sarcobelum (SB) larger than in *C. doroshenkoi*.

Holotype: Vietnam, Southern, Ca Mau Province, Tran Van Thoi District, Tran Hoi Commune, U Minh

Ha National Park, open terrain nearby construction, N09.22434° E104.95909°, 4 m a.s.l., 16 IX 2018, leg. I. Dedov, N. Simov, R. Bekchiev, P. Beron, Coll. No.40329-1A (Fig. 1 A); Paratypes, same locality, 5 adult, 2 juvenile. Coll.No.40329-1B-H.

Description

Body: medium-sized, compact and rounded (in inactive animals). In the living animal mantle lobes fully cover the shell or shell could be seen from more or less narrow slit. (Fig. 2 A). Cephalopodium terminates in caudal fossa with greatly overhanging horn (Fig. 6 A, B). The posterior caudal part not nearly-separated by a deep groove from the rest of the body, and it is not compact nor muscular. Total length of the preserved adult specimen (N2) 15.0–15.1 mm, body width 5.3–5.5 mm. Sole narrow, divided into three zones, the two lateral (0.2–0.7 mm) are slightly more greyish, the central one (0.7–0.9 mm) creamish-white (Fig. 3 A–C), observed in fixed animal (specimen A).

Colouration: Primary colour of mantle is entirely dark greyish-blackish, including the pustules. The keel is only slightly lighter than the rest of the body (Fig. 2 A). In fixed animals the pigment concentrates in darker circles around some of the pustules. Anterior part of body creamish-white with pale greyish patches (Fig. 3 C). Tentacles greyish (Fig. 3 A–C).

Shell (N2) (Fig. 4 A–C): About 2–2.5 fast growing whorls, length 8.1–8.48 mm, width 5.3–5.4 mm, height 2.1–2.3 mm. Upper spire calcareous over periphery, basal part membranaceous. Colour greenish-yellowish. Postapical surface smoother than in *C. doroshenkoi*, but fine irregular radial wrinkles are visible.

Anatomy (Fig. 5 A–C): Atrium is relatively large and bulbous.

Penis and epiphallus, with almost same diameter, externally hard to distinguish, penis shorter. The penile retractor is weak, attached to the border between the flagellum and the epiphallus (not visible on the sketch). Vas deferens entering flagellum/epiphallus junction. Flagellum consisting of two parts: proximal part relatively wider and terminating with small bulbs, containing very long AXT (more than twice longer than in *C. doroshenkoi*); relatively short, bulbiform distal part with less prominent and fewer (about 5 externally visible) folds. Sarcobelum large (larger than in *C. doroshenkoi*), roughly fusiform, with apical

Fig. 1. Localities of species of *Cambodiparmarion* in South Vietnam. A. *Cambodiparmarion bekchievi* Dedov & Vu, sp. nov., Ca Mau Province, U Minh Ha National park; B. *Cambodiparmarion dobroshenkoi*, Kien Giang Province, Mo So Cave; C. cf. *Cambodiparmarion*, Cù Chi Tunnels Historical Park, district of Ho Chi Minh City.

Fig. 2. Alive specimens of *Cambodiparmarion* in South Vietnam. A. *Cambodiparmarion bekchievi* Dedov & Vu, sp. nov., with tropical Colembolla on the mantle; B. *Cambodiparmarion doroshenkoi*; C. cf. *Cambodiparmarion*.

Fig. 3. *Cambodiparmarion bekchievi* Dedov & Vu, sp. nov. – fixed body. A – top view, B – sole, C – lateral view.

Fig. 4. Shell of *Cambodiparmarion bekchievi* Dedov & Vu, sp. nov. A – dorsal view of the shell, B – ventral view of the shell, C – lateral view of the shell. Scale bar: 2 mm.

retractor. Stalk of bursa copulatrix thick and short; reservoir relatively wide.

Etymology

The species is named after the Bulgarian entomologist Dr Rostislav Bekchiev, for his help during the collecting trips in Vietnam.

Cambodiparmarion doroshenkoi Kuznetsov & Kuzminykh, 1999

Materials: Vietnam, Southern, Kien Giang Province, Kien Luong District, Binh An Commune, Ba Nui

Fig. 5. Reproductive system of *Cambodiparmarion*: *C. bekchievi* A – general view, B – penis, C – penial retractor and the entering point of vas deferens; *C. dobroshenkoi*: D – general view, E – penis. Abbreviations: AT – atrium, P – penis, MRP – musculus retractor penis, VD – vas deferens, B – penis, FL – flagellum, AXT – axial thread, SB – sarcobelum, SBR – sarcobelum retractor, BCS – stalk of bursa copulatrix, BC – bursa copulatrix, AG – albumen gland. Scale bar: Fig. 5 A, D – 1 mm; Fig. 5 B, C, E – 200 μ m.

Village, cave Mo So (cave 1), limestone rocks, 10.227652° 104.616249°, 17 m a.s.l., 18 IX 2018, leg. I. Dedov, N. Simov, R. Bekchiev, P. Beron, Coll. No.40334 / 1 adult, 1 juvenile.

Description

Body: medium-sized, compact and rounded (in an inactive living animal). Total length of the preserved

Fig. 6. *Cambodiparmarion* – cephalopodium with the horn and caudal fossa. *C. bekchievi*: A. pustules (PS), B. caudal horn (CH) and caudal fossa (FS); *C. doroshenkoi*: C. caudal horn (CH) and caudal fossa (FS), D. anterior part of the body.

adult specimen (N1) 19.3 mm, body width 5.7 mm. Mantle lobes fully cover the shell or shell could be seen from more or less narrow slit. Cephalopodium terminates in caudal fossa with thick horn (Fig. 6 C). The posterior caudal part (behind visceral hump) not nearly-separated by a deep groove from the rest of the body, and it is not compact and muscular as in genera *Laocaia*, *Muangnua* and *Ostracolethe* (Dedov et al., 2018; Dedov, 2024).

Colouration: Primary colour of the body of living animal is brownish (adult specimen) to dark brownish (juvenile specimen), decorated with white-creamish pustules. Cephalopodium with white-creamish keel (Fig. 2 B). Colouration of the fixed body fit the

description of Kuznetsov & Kuzminykh (1999): mantle lobes dark grey, decorated with white pustules. Anterior part of the body light yellow, with radial interrupted rays. (Fig. 6 D).

Shell (N1) (Fig. 7 A–C, partly broken): the shell of our specimens looks more rounded (most likely, a wrong impression due to the breakage) in comparison with the figure in Kuznetsov & Kuzminykh (1999), but generally follows the description of the authors – ear-shaped, thin, of about 1.5–1.75 whorls, length 4.98 mm (until the break, with correction to over 6–6.5 mm), width 4.6 mm, height 2.7 mm. Upper spire calcareous over periphery, basal part membranaceous. Colour amber. Postapical surface with irregular radial

Fig. 7. *Cambodiparmarion dobroshenkoi* – shell: A – dorsal view of the shell (with restored silhouette), B – ventral view of the shell, C – lateral view of the shell. Scale bar: 1 mm.

wrinkles and faintly visible, widely spaced, locally interrupted spiral striae.

Anatomy (Fig. 5 D, E): Atrium is relatively large and bulbous.

Penis and epiphallus with almost the same diameter, externally hard to distinguish, with almost equal length. Together form weak coiled tube (or “sinuous”, see Kuznetsov & Kuzminykh, 1999). The penile retractor is weak, attached to the border between the flagellum and the epiphallus. Vas deferens entering flagellum/epiphallus junction. Flagellum consisting of two parts: proximal part narrow and relatively long, containing axial thread;

Fig. 8. cf. *Cambodiparmarion* sp. – fixed body. A – top view, B – sole, C – lateral view.

distal part enlarged, with numerous (about 14 externally visible) transversal folds. Sarcobelum large, roughly fusiform, with apical retractor (not visible on the sketch). Stalk of bursa copulatrix is thick and short. The reservoir is relatively wide, and is adjacent to the middle part of the seminal canal.

Cambodiparmarion (?) sp.

Materials: Vietnam, Southern, Cù Chi Tunnels Historical Park, Cù Chi District of Ho Chi Minh City (= Saigon), under leaf litter, N11.14395° E106.46435°, 29 X 2023, leg. I. Dedov, N. Simov, R. Bekchiev, M. Langurov, Coll.No.40620 / 1 juvenile.

During the 2023 expedition to Vietnam, a single semi-slug specimen was found not far from Ho Chi Minh City, which probably also belongs to the genus *Cambodiparmarion*. The specimen was a juvenile, which did not allow for its precise identification, but the habitus and shell characters correspond to those

Fig. 9. Shell of cf. *Cambodiparmarion* sp. A – dorsal view of the shell, B – ventral view of the shell, C – lateral view of the shell. Scale bar: 2 mm.

known for the genus. The animal differs from the two above-mentioned species.

Colouration: Primary colour of mantle is entirely chocolate-brownish, including the pustules. Keel lighter than the rest of the body (Fig. 2 C). In fixed animals (Fig. 8 A–C) the pigment concentrates in dark circles around some of the pustules. Anterior part of body pale creamish-brownish with brownish-greyish patches. Tentacles greyish. Total length of the preserved specimen (N1) 12.1 mm, body width 4.5 mm.

Sole narrow, divided into three zones, the lateral two are pinkish-brownish, the central one is creamish-whitish (Fig. 8 B), observed and measured in fixed animal.

Shell (N1) (Fig. 9 A–C): about 2–2.3 fast growing whorls, length 6.2 mm, width 4.47 mm, height 1.5 mm. Upper spire calcareous over periphery, basal part

membranaceous. Colour transparent amber. Postapical surface more smooth with fine irregular radial wrinkles, as in *C. bekchievi* Dedov & Vu, sp. nov.

Discussion

Distribution of the genus

Finding the genus *Cambodiparmarion* in Vietnam is not a surprise. According to Kuznetsov & Kuzminykh (1999), *C. doroshenkoi* occurs in wet tropical forests near the shore, where it lives on low plants during the wet season, and in thick layer in fallen leaves during the dry season. The locality where *C. doroshenkoi* was found was only about 32 km (straight line) from the Cambodian border and 4 km from the ocean. The new species, *C. bekchievi* Dedov & Vu, sp. nov., was found deeper in the territory of Vietnam (142 km from the Cambodian border, straight line), but also not far from the shore (about 16 km). Far from the shore is the Cù Chi Tunnels Historical Park (about 320 km straight line, *Cambodiparmarion* (?) sp.). All species were found deep in the layer in fallen leaves, in very wet condition in accordance with what was observed by Kuznetsov & Kuzminykh (1999).

There are many photos on the internet identified as *C. doroshenkoi* from Cambodia, Singapore, Thailand (<https://www.gbif.org/>), and even from Vietnam (<https://projectnoah.org/>), coordinates N10.2981 E105.756, in the region of our findings). In some of the photos the specimens vary in the colouration of the mantle, caudal keel, and pustules. Moreover, *C. doroshenkoi* has been reported from Singapore (Chan & Lau, 2021), unfortunately without anatomical evidence. Our finding suggest that the genus is more widely distributed and it can be expected in new localities, as well as possibly new species of the genus could be discovered along the coastlines of South-East Asia (i.e. Vietnam, Cambodia, Malaysia, Singapore, Myanmar).

Colouration of *C. doroshenkoi*

In the original description of the species Kuznetsov & Kuzminykh (1999) wrote: “Mantle lobes dark grey, decorated with white pustules, some of which surrounded by black circles. Anterior part of body light yellow, with radial interrupted grey rays, more

clearly expressed on head and behind it. Tail grey, with crowded light tubercles”.

The description perfectly matches the colouration of the fixed specimens, but the original description (Kuznetsov & Kuzminykh, 1999) does not mention whether the observations were made on live or fixed specimens.

In all our specimens from all three taxa, the pattern when “some of the white pustules are surrounded by black circles” is observed only in fixed specimens, while in live specimens the colouration is uniform (Fig. 2 A–C). According to the information in Kuznetsov & Kuzminykh (1999), all specimens were collected by Andrey Kuznetsov, two years before the publication of the article. In the article itself, this author is noted as deceased. We assume that the article itself has prepared later by Alexandr Kuzminykh, based on the fixed materials and notes of Kuznetsov, and the colouration described in it refers to the fixed specimens of the species. Moreover, almost all photos published on the Internet (including around the type locality of the species) or in more recent publications show colours in the brown range, similar to observed by us (<https://www.gbif.org/>, <https://projectnoah.org/>, Chan & Lau, 2021).

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